

Culture-based Health Care Practices Among Cebuanos in Rural and Urban Areas

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Introduction

Cebu and the entire Philippines have a tradition of folk care medicine which has been passed down through generations since time immemorial. Even after producing doctors and nurses who are renowned around the world, the traditional healing art continues to thrive among the population. The various types of healers are common traditional midwives, traditional masseurs and other traditional specialists for super naturally caused ailments (Montepio, 1986, 1987).

Until recently, little attention had been given to cultural dimensions in nursing literature (McEwen, 2005). Currently, no nursing books have ever discussed about the cultural needs among Cebuanos. Most of the books used in the nursing schools in Cebu City are American, Canadian or European authored. These books present diverse spiritual nursing care with cultural considerations. However, culture-based nursing among Cebuanos are not transcribed. With no culturally congruent formal guides available, Cebuano nurses face a dilemma whether or not to integrate traditional health care practices in nursing care. Between the traditional practice and professional nursing practice, the nurse faces a certain crisis. It is a challenge for nurses who have Cebuano clients to provide culturally congruent nursing care when there are no formal guides available.

Most folk care practices in the Province of Cebu are not fully documented. Well documented lay care practices are only from neighboring regions. There is a need to textually recognize these generic care practices to provide literature for nurses caring Cebuano clients to help them evaluate their planned interventions with cultural considerations. This would add to the field of nursing knowledge and would help develop culturally congruent care plans. This study might identify folk care practices that are acceptable to nursing discipline and help modify lay care practices that need to be modified. According to Leininger (1994), these care constructs and patterns must be fully documented, understood, and used to ensure that culturally based care becomes the major guide to cultural nursing therapy and is used to explain or predict nursing practices. Moreover, nursing diagnoses and medical diagnoses that are not culturally based and known are serious problems for cultures that lead to unfavorable and sometimes serious outcomes (Tomey & Alligood, 2002).

Theoretical Background

Since the Cebuano health belief system is deeply tied with culture (Semics LLC, 1997) and that their folk care practices are different from other cultures, the researcher aims to understand the Cebuano generic care practices with the aid of Madeleine Leininger's Culture Care Theory. This theory is based on the belief that people of different cultures inform and are capable of guiding professionals to receive the kind of care they desire or need (Tomey & Alligood, 2002). Leininger affirms that care is the core of nursing and this is the heart of the model. Leininger manages to unify nursing, the nursing process and caring. This combination results in the optimal process of developing cultural sensitivity and treatment.

Leininger recognized insufficiency in the nursing practice, the deficiency of cultural awareness. Leininger's pioneering work combined concepts from anthropology and nursing, merging culture and nursing care. The transformation resulted in a more holistic nursing view, in contrast to the traditional medical model (Tomey & Alligood, 2002). The professional nurse must understand, embrace and respect these culturally based spiritual beliefs and practices in order to provide culturally congruent care. This comprehensive approach would assure the care for the whole person and not just the illness (Dwyer, 2006).

Leininger's model was in the shape of a rising sun. The outer ring was the worldview of the client. The next ring was the various values, beliefs, and life ways of the client. The model suggested that the world view and social structure were important areas nurses should explore and investigate using the

seven dimensions. These dimensions included: (1) Cultural Values and Life ways; (2) Religious, Philosophical, and Spiritual Beliefs; (3) Economic; (4) Educational; (5) Technological; (6) Kinship and Social Ties; and (7) Political and Legal Factors. These factors greatly influenced cultural practices and the well being of clients. As nurses develop a thorough understanding of the background and formative factors in the life of the client, they construct care expressions, patterns, and practices. Ethnonursing, ethnography, life histories, life stories, photography, and phenomenological methods were used to provide a holistic approach to study cultural behavior in diverse environmental context (Tomey & Alligood, 2002; Kozier et al, 2004; Dwyer, 2006; Shives, 2008).

One key component of Leininger's theory was the concept of generic care or folk care, which referred to the remedies passed on from one generation to another within a particular culture (Tomey & Alligood, 2002). In the Bisayan setting, Galleon (1976), Aparece (2006) and Ting (2008) identified that the sick individual ask for "tambal" (cure) from the "tambalan" (medicine man), which was a general term, who also acted as the "albularyu" (native spiritual herbalist), manghihilut" (native spiritual masseurs), "urasyunan" (one who utters Latin-Bisayan verses to cure illness), "mananayhup" (healer who blows air softly while incantations are muttered), "manunutho" (curer who squirts saliva on afflicted part of the patient) and the "mananabang" (midwife). Typically patients relied on these traditional practices long before seeking professional care (Mercado, 1977, 1992; Lieban, 1978). The generic or folk care among Bisayan is rooted towards the principle of balance or "timbang" which includes a set of fundamental principles and recently attached to Christian practices. Practices among Cebuanos includes: (1) Anting-anting, habak, panagang, sumpa"; (2) avoid inappropriate behavior; (3) "Binignit"; (4) "Butung"; (5) "Dili maligo"; (6) "Gabâ"; (7) "Gamut"; (8) "Gidaut o gibarang"; (9) "Haplas"; (10) "Ilimnun"; (11) "Ipasuka"; (12) "Ipautot"; (13) Knee walking; (14) Laying of hands; (15) "Magputi"; (16) "Novena"; (17) "Pagdagkot"; (18) "Pagpanubay o pagpanusisi"; (19) "Pamisa"; (20) "Pangala"; (21) "Pasmu"; (22) "Rigalu o halad"; (23) "Sayaw sa Dibusyon"; and (24) "Tuub" (Mercado, 1977; Licauco, 1982; Basiigo, 1994; Perez, 1999; Pambid; 2000; McBride, 2001; Aparece, 2003; Becker, 2003; Aparece, 2006; Sanchez, 2007; Ting, 2008; Wikipedia, 2008).

The generic care component together with the professional care-cure system component is interlocked with the meaningful nursing care. With these three essential ingredients intertwined, there is quality healthcare for the client (Tomey & Alligood, 2002). Eventually, the knowledge derived from the interlocked components brings about cultural care decision and actions (Dwyer, 2006). The main purpose is to discover the cultural views or people's emic views about care as they know, believe, and practice care and then use this knowledge with appropriate etic professional knowledge to guide care practices.

To achieve this imperative goal, Leininger delineated three elements or care decisions and actions that nurses needed to reflect on in providing culturally congruent care. This included: (1) culture care preservation and maintenance - this occurred when nursing care preservation or maintenance was used to enable people of a particular culture to retain or preserve relevant care values so that they could maintain their well-being, recover from illness, or face handicaps and/or death; (2) culture care accommodation or negotiation - this involved the actions and decisions that help people in a culture adapt to or negotiate with others for a beneficial or satisfying health outcome with professional care providers; (3) culture care repatterning or restructuring - this was used to help clients change or modify their health care patterns to provide a way of life more beneficial or healthier while still respecting their cultural patterns and beliefs (Tomey & Alligood, 2002; Kozier et al, 2004; Shives, 2008).

The Problem

The purpose of this study was to analyze the culture-based health care practices among well and ill Cebuanos. This study was conducted in the Province of Cebu for the year 2008.

Specifically, the study attempted to answer the following questions:

1. How were the lived experiences of Cebuanos in the use of culture-based health care practiced in the;
 - 1.1. urban area; and
 - 1.2. rural area?
2. How were the culture-based health care practices provided by the Tambalans in the:

- 2.1. urban area; and
- 2.2. rural area?
3. How were these culture-based health care practices being influenced by:
 - 3.1. religious and philosophical factor;
 - 3.2. kinship and social factor;
 - 3.3. political and legal factor;
 - 3.4. cultural values, beliefs and lifeways factor;
 - 3.5. economic factor;
 - 3.6. technological factor; and
 - 3.7. educational factor?
4. How could the culture-based health care practices be integrated in the professional nursing care considering:
 - 4.1. culture care preservation and maintenance;
 - 4.2. culture care accommodation or negotiation; and
 - 4.3. culture care repatterning or restructuring?

Research Methodology

This study employed the qualitative design utilizing in-depth analysis to provide accurate descriptions to document the lived folk care practices among Cebuanos through fieldwork. Furthermore, this utilized ethn nursing method which applied ethnography in nursing. This qualitative study had an anthropological viewpoint to delineate care as a culturally and professionally determined phenomenon.

The researcher chose Tugbongan, which is one of the barangays of the municipality in Consolacion, as the rural representative site for this study. Tugbongan is a middle income to low income community, leading the residents to choose more cheap yet cost-effective health care services. The researcher chose Canduman, which is one of the barangays of Mandaue, as the urban representative site for this study. The barangay used to be an agricultural area but now it has become an industrialized zone in the early 80's. Canduman seems to belong to a high income to low income community. This allowed Candumanons to choose between a continuum of highly spendthrift to cheap yet cost-effective health care services.

The researcher approached potential Cebuano lay informants through the help of trusted individuals, known as "gatekeepers". These potential participants must: (1) be a resident of Cebu for at least fifteen years; (2) be born and reared in the Province of Cebu; (3) be between ages thirty-five to sixty-five years old; and (4) have not lived outside Cebu Province.

The researcher used the "big net" approach, mingled and conversed with as many members per barangay. Twenty-five informants per site were purposively identified from the pool of potential informants. Although there were twenty-five per site, five key informants per site were selected purposively, guided by the ethnographer's judgments. Twenty-five informants per site were also purposively selected for the focused group discussion.

The Tambalans were the key informants of the study; because they have hands-on experience with the Cebuanos' culture-based spiritual care practices.

When the data from the Cebuanos and Tambalans were available, the researcher consulted anthropologists, historians, religious, community nurses, psychologists and sociologists who have practiced their profession in Cebu City. These experts were also key informants for this study. Their insights, expertise and knowledge about the phenomenon were shared with the researcher.

The main instrument of the study was the researcher himself. The concept of researcher as instrument was used frequently to describe the significant role ethnographers play in analyzing and interpreting a culture (Polit & Beck, 2004).

To facilitate the researcher in gathering data, a well thought-out interview schedule was utilized. However, the data gathered was not only limited to what was inquired in the interview schedule. The researcher made use of field notes where observations, reports, life stories and informal conversations

were transcribed. Observations, reports, and life stories were very helpful in demonstrating actual events that would support the culture-based health care practices among Cebuanos. Tape recorder, still camera and video camera were also used as instruments of this study.

Category schemes and thematic guides were formulated after all the relevant data were collected. This was devised to aid coding of the transcribed interviews and observations. This was also utilized to aid a trouble-free and systematic data analysis.

The data analysis based from Leininger's (1991) four phases of analysis for ethnographic qualitative data was utilized. The first phase necessitated description of documented raw data from interviews, participatory observation, reflections and diaries. This phase supported and facilitated several tasks that help to organize and manage the mass of narrative data. Audiotapes, videotapes and field notes were transcribed in verbatim. The researcher checked and ensured that transcriptions were accurate which validly reflect the totality of the interview experience. The second phase consisted of the identification of descriptions in relation to the view of care. Category schemes or thematic guides were developed to organize the data. The third phase entailed discovery and formulation of repetitive patterns of care and an analysis of the context in which they occurred. The data were read in their entirety and coded for correspondence to different categories to aid the researcher in accessing its parts without repeatedly rereading the entire documents. The last phase involved abstracting major themes, presentation of findings and drafting of major constructs of care with the aid of documents from the different culture care models, medical models and ethnographic books.

Findings

Folk Health Care practices by the Cebuanos and Tambalans in the rural and urban areas have both similarities and differences. Though practices were similar, differences were presented in the procedures. The differences in the procedures rely on the availability of resources in the area. Procedures in the rural area were more detailed and complex since the resources were readily available. Procedures in the urban area were simple since the resources were limited and alternatives were utilized.

Some traditional practices were believed to be effective among Cebuanos. Western forms of treatment though believed to be effective, genuine and beneficial were less prioritized.

It was observed that the spiritual, social, political, cultural, economic, technological and educational factors were all part of the entire package among Cebuano health care system and were not divisible. These factors were observed to overlap with each other.

Safe Cebuano health care practices were identified and were found to be the source of strength among Cebuanos. Familial involvement, Cebuanos' relationship towards the community and Cebuano values and beliefs were observed to be part of health care decision making. These practices should be preserved and maintained.

"Bahala na", "gaba", "sigurista", "tambag", "ulaw", "pakigkauban", and the Cebuano concept of the collective "I" ("kita man gud") are Cebuano culture-based practices that retain relevant care values that could maintain health and well being. "Hilut", "herbularyu", religious health practices, and "panghimasmu" are safe traditional practices with technical benefits. "Tutho", "tayhup", "palina", "kabkab sa kabuhi" and "hilut sa tyan" were found to provide health risks.

With enough acquaintance with the Cebuano cultural structure, this study improves: (1) nurses' knowledge in the field of cultural nursing, and (2) the quality of health care services they render.

Conclusions

Using the Culture Care Theory of Madeleine Leininger, the researcher accounted the beneficial information that nurses use in their practice when dealing with Cebuano clients. With enough acquaintance with the Cebuano cultural structure, this study improves: (1) nurses' knowledge in the field of cultural nursing, and (2) the quality of health care services they render.

The cultural construct among Cebuanos was evaluated and acknowledged the influences of the overlapping factors in the health care decision making among Cebuanos. The three important care decisions and actions in providing Cebuano-based care have to be observed. This included: (1) Cebuano culture care preservation and maintenance (2) Cebuano culture care accommodation or negotiation;

and (3) Cebuano culture care repatterning or restructuring.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Nurses with Cebuano clients must familiarize the Cebuano culture including its culture-based practices that are helpful in drafting a culturally congruent nursing care plan for Cebuano clients.
2. Nurses must identify the factors and assess its influence to culture-based health care decision among Cebuano clients.
3. Nurses must preserve Cebuano culture-based practices that retain their relevant care values and practices so they could maintain their health and well being.
4. Nurses must collaborate with the Tambalan when Cebuano clients submit themselves to both type of treatments.
5. Nurses must monitor the different Cebuano culture-based health care practices and should assess for its safety.
6. Nurses must provide health teachings to correct the practice of "tutho", "tayhup", "palina", "kabkab sa kabuhi" and "hilut sa tiyan", since these culture-based health care practices could provide health risks.
7. Nurses should provide health teachings to Tambalans about the danger of prescribing medications without proper professional medical education;
8. Nurse educators in Cebu should integrate these Cebuano culture-based practices in the curriculum. Nurse authors are encouraged to include these Cebuano culture-based practices in their manuscripts to help in the dissemination of this relevant information that could help provide a culturally congruent nursing care plan for Cebuano clients.
9. Trainings, seminars, lectures and demonstrations should be provided to Tambalans by qualified professionals.
10. The Government should Regulate the Tambalans' Practice in the Philippines.
11. Standards for the Cebuano Folk Care Practice as a Complimentary Treatment should be drafted and implemented by the Philippine Nurses Association, and other medical and paramedical associations.
12. Future researchers interested on ethnonursing methods could do an in-depth study on a more specific culture-based health care practice.
13. Replications are encouraged to confirm the results of this study and to supplement information not covered by this study.
14. A more in-depth, controlled and specific studies are encouraged utilizing a more sophisticated methodology not limited to qualitative design.
15. Case studies, evaluative studies and experimental studies on "himnasmu" as treatment for some Psychiatric disorder could be a helpful future Psychiatric-Mental Health Nursing study.
16. To address the knowledge and skills needed for Cebuano culture-care, a framework for delivering services could serve as guidelines. Nurses are encouraged:
 - 16.1. To recognize that as cultural beings, they might hold attitudes and beliefs that could detrimentally influence their perceptions and interactions with clients who were culturally different from themselves.
 - 16.2. To recognize the importance of cultural sensitivity or responsiveness to knowledge and understanding about ethically, culturally different individuals.
 - 16.3. As educators, to employ the constructs of culturalism and diversity in nursing education.
 - 16.4. As a culturally sensitive professional, to recognize the importance of conducting culture-centered and ethical nursing research among person from different cultural backgrounds.
 - 16.5. To apply culturally appropriate skills in clinical and other applied nursing practices.

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